

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue II, February 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The MATATAG K-10 Curriculum: A Leap Towards Quality Education in the Philippines

GENEROSO DOCTOR CAYETANO, MAM-AS

TEACHER III/Teacher-In-Charge

Tampi Elementary School

Division of Sorsogon Province

Region V

A light of innovation shines through the colorful tapestry of Philippine educational reform, changing the face of basic education with its transformative glow. The Department of Education (DepEd) created the groundbreaking MATATAG K-10 Curriculum, which is set to completely transform the educational process for students in kindergarten through tenth grade. This curriculum overhaul, with its deliberate balance of simplification and improvement, aims to unravel the maze of overly complex curricula and infuse classrooms all around the country with fresh energy. With its mission to advance fundamental abilities while negotiating the waves of cognitive complexity, MATATAG gives educators and students a reason for optimism. Though change is anticipated, some concerns remain: Will students' potential actually be unlocked by this more efficient approach? Will the transition to educational excellence be easier with the phased implementation? Come along with us as we explore MATATAG K-10—a journey into the center of educational evolution, where aspiration meets innovation and a better future is promised.

The MATATAG K-10 is a revised curriculum that the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) has recently introduced for students in Kindergarten through Grade 10. By concentrating on fundamental skills and minimizing the number of learning areas, the new curriculum seeks to simplify the existing one.

It was discovered that the previous curriculum was too demanding on teachers and students, with far too many lessons or subjects. MATATAG K-10 Curriculum was created as a solution to this problem. By balancing cognitive demands, it helps students advance through grade levels and acquire higher-order thinking abilities. Five learning areas—Language, Reading and Literacy, Math, Makabansa, and Good Manners and Right Conduct—replace the previous seven in the curriculum.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

About 70% of the current curriculum will be eliminated in the MATATAG K–10 Curriculum, bringing the total number of learning competencies down from over 11,000 to about 3,600. It is anticipated that this substantial cut will allow more time for what DepEd called foundational skills for improved learning outcomes.

Beginning with the 2024–2025 academic year, the MATATAG Curriculum will be implemented gradually. Kinder, Grade 1, Grade 4, and Grade 7 students will be covered. Other grade levels will progressively switch to the new curriculum over the ensuing years.

In order to guarantee a seamless rollout of the updated curriculum, DepEd has indicated that it would be willing to train educators in private schools¹. Teachers of students in Kindergarten, First Grade, Fourth Grade, and Seventh Grade—the grade levels where the phased implementation will begin—will receive special training.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10643806

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.